

Keywords:

#data, #OpenScience, #FAIRprinciples, #Reliance, #EUFar #ResearchObjects, #EOSCinPractice

Collaborative Knowledge Sharing: a case study on EU FAR project

Leveraging Zenodo, RoHub, RDA, and EOSC Marketplace for data sharing and collaboration

The EOSCFuture.eu/RDA open calls

The open calls managed by the Research Data Alliance (RDA) with funding from EOSCFuture.eu aim to bring data initiatives closer to EOSC and provide EOSC with expertise, tools, best practices, and standards from the global research data community, with a total million Euro reserved to fund over 65 grantees over 12 open calls.

The Project Involved

EU FAR – EU Funds by Area Results - was supported under the RDA Open Call for Cross Disciplinary Science Adoption Grants #1 and it was implemented by the Research Institute for Quality of Life from September 2022 until April 2023. The key objective of the project was to stimulate the development of open data on EU funding, in line with FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability). Information publicly displayed by the project is focused on EU funds absorbed by local governments in Romania (LAU 2 level) from 2014 to 2020, with a special focus on rural areas.

The Research Community

The EU FAR user community is mainly composed of scholars from sociology, public management, geography and economics as well as academics interested in general in open science practices. EU FAR reuses open governmental data; consequently, stakeholders from public sphere will be interested in the increased re-usage of data from public institutions.

Monica Marin

Researcher at the Research Institute for Quality of Life, Romanian Academy, EU FAR

"EOSC services and tools provide a wider dissemination for project outputs. The key idea of open science is therefore promoted in a research ecosystem where re-sharing of data is not always the rule. Larger dissemination can provide the impetus to build similar databases in other EU countries."

The Challenge

The main challenge EU FAR addresses is the lack of granular data on EU funding. In Romania, open governmental data still include errors on key aggregators (mainly LAU 2 code) and are not fully aligned with the FAIR movement. Additionally, a thorough methodological approach is needed to aggregate data between budgetary years and have a comprehensive overall picture of what has actually happened with EU funding at the lowest administrative level, that of the municipality. Part of these challenges are valid not only for Romania, but also for other EU countries. Especially in post-communist countries, territorial disparities remain a significant issue, with rural areas placed at a disadvantage on multiple dimensions.

EOSC service or tool used

All project deliverables are available on [Zenodo](#), and one of the key deliverables of the project – EU FAR database – is available on [RoHub](#) as well in [ČSDA – Czech Social Data Archive](#), which is part of [CESSDA](#). Additionally, project outputs are also available on [Open Science Framework](#) and [Scipedia](#), which are also promoted in various research available from EOSC Marketplace. We found very useful ideas in training materials available from EOSC, on various topics: open science, research data, FAIR sharing, and FAIR promotion.

Keywords:

#data, #OpenScience, #Ruralareas, #Gnomee, #AthenaRC #ResearchObjects, #EOSCinPractice

Useful tips & tricks

We initially searched EOSC services and tools when submitting the research proposal. However, in the meantime, EOSC had evolved, and we were happy to discover better search options as well as the availability of useful training materials. Therefore, being constantly informed about EOSC pays off. Additionally, we would like to express our sincere thanks to the Czech Social Data Archive for agreeing to publish our database, as the Romanian partner from CESSDA is no longer functional. Being now part of CESSDA greatly increases the discoverability of the EU FAR database.

Benefits and impact

EOSC services and tools provide a wider dissemination for project outputs. The key idea of open science is therefore promoted in a research ecosystem where re-sharing of data is not always the rule. Larger dissemination can provide the impetus to build similar databases in other EU countries. The EU FAR database aggregates public open data on the volume of EU funds absorbed by each municipality (LAU 2) level in Romania for the entire programming period of 2014-2020. Data are converted into euro at constant 2010 prices per inhabitant to provide comparable data both between Romanian municipalities and, eventually, other European territorial administrative units. Maps at national, regional (NUTS 2) or county (NUTS 3) levels illustrate the results on EU funding. Analysis of spatial disparities between rural areas is part of a working paper. Additionally, a policy brief in plain language explains which are the key areas at stake and the needed policy actions.

Why do I need RDA?

We would also like to mention the role of RDA: the plenary meeting and its co-located events provided ample opportunities for networking, brainstorming and exchanging lessons learned. The RDA Overview for the Social Sciences Report (October 2022) and the Metadata Standards Catalog WG Final Report were also very useful documents in the planning stages of the project.

Useful material related to this story

rda-alliance.org

Why do I need EOSC?

EOSC represents a platform for the wide dissemination of research results. It is highly useful in connecting researchers from various disciplines and countries, which is key to further developing the EU FAR database with similar initiatives across EU countries. By showcasing different research results from our projects or other relevant projects, EOSC services and tools promote open access to research products and reduce the risk of duplication of efforts, which is critical to advancing the research agenda.

Across disciplines

EU FAR is a cross-disciplinary project, with research results that are valuable for sociology, economics, geography and public management. The project team aims to further facilitate cross-fertilization of results by seeking to also further improve the reusability part of open governmental data.

Limitations and future improvement

As publications represent one of the key indicators for evaluating researchers, better cross-linkages between data repositories and publications repositories would be very valuable. Some of the preprint and journal platforms have already done this, but further improvements would be beneficial for the research community in general.

Liked this
#EOSCinPractice
story?

Follow
@EOSCFuture
for more!

Share your own #EOSCinPractice story here